

Importance of Ilha Comprida (São Paulo State, Brazil) for the Sanderlings (*Calidris Alba*) Migration

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ABSTRACT

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Ilha Comprida beach (São Paulo State, Brazil) is an important site for migration sanderlings (*Calidris alba*). This paper analyses the seasonal occurrence of sanderlings at Ilha Comprida and the impact of human disturbance. The results show that Ilha Comprida area is an stopover site during December but not during winter months (June, July and August), and the abundance of sanderlings may be reduced by 90% due to high human disturbance levels. Ilha Comprida is an alternative migration route to the south and an important foraging and rest area for *Calidris alba*.

ADDITIONAL INDEX WORDS. *Sanderlings, Calidris alba, migration, shorebird.*

INTRODUCTION

Neartic shorebirds that migrate to South America for the nonbreeding season reach their wintering sites by several routes (MORRISON, 1984; MYERS *et al.*, 1990). Ilha Comprida is an shorebird migratory stopover site, at the south Coast of São Paulo State, Brazil where sanderlings (*Calidris alba*) are usually seen in groups during Spring and Summer (BARBIERI *et al.*, 2000).

Most New World Sanderlings nest on dry Arctic Tundra of 72° N, mainly on islands at the Canadian Arctic Archipelago and especially at Prince of Wales Island (MAYERS *et al.*, 1990), northwestern Greenland and Baffin Island, the central Canadian Arctic Islands, and the Taimyr Peninsula (CRAMP and SIMMONS, 1983). Sanderlings migrate along the American continent to non reproductive areas e.g. Lagoa do Peixe in Rio Grande do Sul (Brazil), Tierra del Fuego (Argentina) and coasts of Peru and Chile (MYERS *et al.*, 1990). These species that migrates long distances, is specialized in habitat prey interaction, and are concentrated on sandy beaches (BURGER and GOCHFELD, 1991), such as Ilha Comprida. Although the diets of shorebirds may be catholic, prey with different sizes are commonly taken by different species, which may also display some special separation up the shore (BROWN and McLACHLAN, 1990).

The route followed by this species, when abandoning the non reproductive site in their migration to the North (March-April),

can be traced through the Amazon region and the southeastern coast of the United States. During its southern migration (September-October), the birds leave the breeding areas to feed at the non reproductive site, going through the United States western coast, Caribbean, North of Brazil through the Amazon, and southward to Lagoa do Peixe (MYERS *et al.*, 1990).

During their migration, this bird depends on marine coastal habitats, mainly on sandy beaches (MYERS *et al.*, 1979). Insufficient information exists with respect to the migration routes, stopover points, and provisioning for *Calidris alba* on the coast of Brazil. Ilha Comprida beach is high relevant for *Calidris alba* migration where it occurs during Spring, Summer and in the beginning of the Autumn. The present paper shows the importance of Ilha Comprida as a migration route and feeding ground for *C. alba* and demonstrates the effects of tourism on the species abundance at foraging areas.

METHODS

Study Area

Ilha Comprida is located at the Southern coast of São Paulo State, and is part of the Ribeira de Iguape hydrographic basin, whose mouth marks the northern limit of the Iguape - Cananéia - Paranaguá estuarine complex. This island is about 72 Km long

and 3 km wide on average.

Ilha Comprida was formed by the accumulation of sandy sediments and is a prominent landscape at the southern coast of São Paulo State (lat 47° 50' W 24° 52' S). However, subject to great fragility to intensive anthropogenic occupation. Its vegetation is basically composed of swamps, dunes, scrub forests and mangroves together with its resident fauna, visitor birds from the Northern and the Southern Hemisphere.

It is a recent quaternary barrier island of marine origin (SUGUIU and MARTINS, 1987). The Island is favorable for tourism, being a strip of approximately 72 Km long of sandy beach, interrupted by small streams, forming a beautiful scenery. It is disorderly occupied by secondary residents but a few traditional fishing communities still survive. Lunar tides have an amplitude of about 1.50 m. The sea level is lowered by the prevailing northeasterly wind, and raised by the southerly winds. The beach has a gentle slope (U40 to U60) and as a result the swash zone is wide, generally about 15 m. In this zone, invertebrates occur in high densities.

Methodology

Bird censuses were carried out from 4 June 1998 to 6 May 1999, along all the stretch of 72 km of beach from the locality of Boqueirão Sul and northward to Icapara Channel (Figure 1). Coastal birds were counted on the northward journey from a vehicle moving at about 40Km/h along the lower beach. Such methodology was used by VOOREN and CHIARADIA, (1990) and proposed by BIBBY et al. (1992) for sandy beaches. The censuses were done in the morning periods from about 08:00 to 11:30 h, during ebb tides, when weather and traffic conditions were good. Weekly sampling added up a total of 48 samples (4 samples per month). Each census had minimum duration of 2:30 hours of observation and maximum of 4:00 hours.

Binoculars (7X50 and 20X60) were used for observations. The sighted birds were identified, counted and photographed. Bird activities and human disturbance were further registered simultaneously. Two anthropogenic disturbances were defined: people and vehicles circulating at the beach. Frequency of sanderlings behaviors (alert, run, flight, indifferent) when foraging at Ilha Comprida beach in relation to human approach were registered.

RESULTS

The results indicate that *Calidris alba* is a species of common occurrence at the beach of Ilha Comprida, as regularly observed from the September to Autumn season. Individuals of *Calidris alba* begin to arrive in the area at the end of September, with average of 77.5 individuals, reaching a maximum abundance in December when average of 175 individuals were detected (Figure 2). In the end of March and beginning of April a clear decrease in the number of individuals occurs (averages of 24.2 and 6.75 individuals respectively), that coincides with the returning period to the Northern Hemisphere. The counts indicate that most of the population starts to abandon Ilha Comprida in February, and are not being sighted in the end of May as well as in winter (South Hemisphere).

They were found foraging with other species forming heterospecific groups, with the following occurrence frequencies: *Charadrius semipalmatus* (44,26%), *Pluvialis dominica* (26,22%), *Calidris fuscicollis* (24,59%) and *Calidris melanotos* (4,91%) (Table 1).

In the great majority of time (92%) the bird groups were foraging at the beach and in just a few cases (8%) sanderlings were observed in resting behavior.

Figure 1. Localization of Ilha Comprida at the south coast of São Paulo State Brazil.

Figure 2. Monthly frequency distribution of the abundance of sanderling along Ilha Comprida beach.

Table 1. Frequency of other shorebirds in heterospecific foraging flocks at Ilha Comprida where *C. alba* was always present.

Species	Number of occurrence	Relative importance of the species in %
<i>Charadrius semipalmatus</i>	27	44,26
<i>Pluvialis dominica</i>	16	26,22
<i>Calidris fuscicollis</i>	15	24,59
<i>Calidris melanotos</i>	3	4,91
Total	61	100 %

Sanderlings react to human disturbances by flying, running away and standing in alert state. In 70% of the cases, when people approached to about 50 meters, sanderlings flew away. When human approaches were around 100 meters the sanderlings ran away in 55% of the cases. The state of alert was observed in 55% of the cases, when the approach was around 150 meters (Table 2).

A negative exponential relationship of the number of people in the beach (tourists) and the sanderlings abundance (Figure 3) was observed. The same tendency occurred when considering number of vehicles at the beach, i.e. as the number of vehicles increased the abundance of *Calidris alba* (Figure 4) was exponentially reduced.

DISCUSSION

The only research on beach bird composition of Ilha Comprida carried out so far was by BARBIERI et al. (2000), however, it is

one of the best areas to study shorebirds in the Southeastern coast of Brazil. The results suggest that this zone constitutes an passage and foraging area for *Calidris alba* during its migration to the southern areas of South America, such as the Lagoa do Peixe in Brazil and Tierra del Fuego in Argentina. MYERS et al. (1990) evaluating the sanderling migration routes, mentioning that they fly through the Brazilian inland to reach the Lagoa do Peixe at Rio Grande do Sul, Southern Brazil, but failed to mention any routes on the Brazilian coast. SICK (1997) however says that among the arctic plovers *C. alba* is the most frequently found at the Brazilian beaches, occurring along the whole Brazilian coast in small groups being found even at night in Copacabana beach, Rio de Janeiro and near Recife city (Pernambuco State) from the end of August to the middle of May. The present paper supports Ilha Comprida is an stopover area, for feeding and resting of migrating sanderlings.

The groups begin to arrive in the end of September reaching the peak in December. From February onwards the frequency decrease

Table 2. Frequency of sanderlings behaviors when foraging at Ilha Comprida beach in relation to human approach.

Distance of the human (In meters)	Types of Behavior of sanderlings			
	Alert	Run	Flight	Indifferent
0-50	-	30%	70%	-
50-100	5%	55%	40%	-
100-150	55%	35%	10%	-
150-200	45%	25%	5%	25%

Figure 3. Relation of sanderlings abundance with respect to people along Ilha Comprida beach.

reaching the lowest number of individuals in April and May. Studies by BELTON (1984) recorded that the migration of the sanderlings, heading for Northern Hemisphere, occurred in April-May consistent with the results of this study, which explains the decreasing of individuals during those months at Ilha Comprida.

Ilha Comprida Island belongs to the Iguapé-Paranaguá estuarine complex which was considered the most productive zone of the Southern Atlantic Ocean (UICN, 1992). Several species of beach birds commonly use this environment for feeding (BARBIERI and SATO, 2000). Among them *Calidris alba* is specialized in habitat interaction and prey, and concentrate in large numbers in sandy beaches (BURGER and GOCHFELD, 1991). Sanderlings typically feed close to the water, running down the beach slope between waves to probe the sand (BROWN and MCLACHLAN, 1990).

The beach of Ilha Comprida where *Calidris alba* feed and rest is also used by tourists and as a "road" with free car access. Human presence generates visible disturbances, mainly for the birds that are resting during the high tide, forcing them to fly leading to an unnecessary loss of energy, as registered by BURGER (1986). The loss of energy can be vital for birds that migrate long distances (DUNN et al., 1988), e.g. sanderlings. The island is facing a fast urbanization process that began in the middle of the 1980 s. Extensive plane and dune areas are favorable for real estate speculation, which were first ignored, due to the desire to be closer to the beach. Human disturbance at Ilha Comprida is altering the insular landscape, mainly due to the real estate speculation associated with tourism and leisure activities.

The sanderling demonstrated very little tolerance to the presence

Figure 4. Relation of sanderlings abundance to vehicles at Ilha Comprida beach.

of human and vehicles presence (Figure 3 and 4). The negative relationship between abundance of the sanderlings and the number of vehicles and people at the beach is of great concern. BURGER and GOCHFELD (1991) indicated that the number of people within 100 m of foraging sanderlings was a significant contributor to variations in time devoted to their foraging. They examined the effects of people presence, according to time of the day. When more people were present, there were significant negative correlation between time devoted to feeding and the time sanderlings flew or ran away due to people presence within 10 and 100 m. PFISTER *et al.*, (1991) showed a change in the distribution pattern of sanderlings on the beach due to vehicle disturbance. The sanderling seems to show a steady response to different disturbance levels; other birds such as the short-billed dowitcher seems to be very sensitive to a disturbance level between 10 and 40 vehicles; at that point the vehicles present a sharp response at high disturbance levels (PFISTER *et al.* 1991).

KLEIN (1995) studied the effects of ecotourism on distribution of waterbirds in a wildlife refuge, says that human activity was much greater along the drive than along the crossdike, where only foot traffic is permitted. Although the approach of humans on foot seemed to be the most disruptive action of visitors (KLEIN, 1993), traffic volume was the more important variable.

CONCLUSIONS

There is a need of more detailed studies to identify shorebirds migratory routes along the Brazilian coast. It is also necessary and of fundamental importance to determine which areas are used by each of the several species, in order to protect them. The present paper shows that Ilha Comprida is one of those areas that need to be protected, and environmental planning required to minimize the effects of tourism on the sanderlings population. The number of

visitors could be limited or the refuge for bird could be delimited. Results of changed management practices could be documented by defining goals for waterbird use and measuring them with the methods of this study.

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